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EVALUATION OF ANTHELMINTIC ACTION OF *EMBLICA OFFICINALIS* LEAVES EXTRACT ON INDIAN EARTH WORM

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ABSTRACT

The aim of present study highlights the evaluation of anthelmintic activity of *Emblica officinalis* leave extract in experimental adult Indian earthworm *Pheretima posthuma*. The shade dried leaves were extracted with ethyl alcohol and water. The different concentrations of water and ethyl alcohol extracts (100 mg/ml and 150mg/ml) were found to possess good vermifugal activity and the results were compared with standard drug Albendazole.

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INTRODUCTION

The world health organization (WHO) has estimated that approximately 80% of the world's population depends on traditional medicines for meeting their primary health care needs. Helminthes is the disease that causes problems for human beings as well as for animals. Most diseases caused by helminthes are of a chronic nature and probably cause more morbidity. The disease is highly prevalent particularly in third world countries due to poor management practices. The plant kingdom still holds many species of plants containing substances of medicinal value which have yet to be discovered and large numbers of plants are constantly being screened for their pharmacological value in addition to the already exploited plants [1]. Increasing problems of development of resistance in helminthes against anthelmintics have led to screening medicinal plants for their anthelmintic activity [2, 3].

The helminthes parasites are mainly live in human body intestinal tract, but they are also live in tissue, or their larvae migrate in to the tissue [4]. Anthelmintics are drug that either kill (vermicide) or, reduce the number of helminthes parasites in the intestinal tract or tissues of the body [5]. Normally Helminths are a class of eukaryotic parasites Helminths (worms) can be divided into three groups: cestodes, or tapeworms; nematodes, or roundworms; and trematodes, or flukes [6]. *Emblica officinalis* is an important plant of India. This plant was profound medicinal used in anaemia, jaundice, dyspepsia, hemorrhage disorders, diabetes, asthma and bronchitis. The literature survey revealed that fruits of *Emblica Officinalis* show sufficient anthelmintic activity against earthworm *pheretima posthuma* [7] but leaf extract has yet not been screened for anthelmintic activity. Therefore objective of this work was to assess the anthelmintic activity of *Emblica Officinalis* leaves.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Collection & authentication of plant

The leaves of *Emblica officinalis* were collected from the surroundings of Priyadarshani Yashodhara College of pharmacy. The leaves were identified and authenticated by the Department of Botany, S.P. College, Chandrapur.

Extraction methodology

The leaves were dried under shade, coarsely powdered. The 400gm of dried leaves of *Emblica officinalis* extracted with ethanol and water separately for 72 hour at 50⁰ C, refluxed for 48hrs and boiled with activated charcoal (about 1 g) to remove hung and pure plant extract was collected [8]. The extracts obtained were evaporated under vacuum to remove the solvent completely. These crude extracts were stored at low temperature.

Phytochemical investigations on extract

Extract samples were dissolved in suitable solvents and used for qualitative analysis of key phytochemical constituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, saponins, steroids, tannins, proteins, quinones coumarins, glycosides, and carbohydrates. Qualitative phytochemical analyses of *E. officinalis* was performed according to the methods of [9, 10, 11].

Test for detection of alkaloid

1 ml of extract was taken in a test tube, followed by addition of 1 ml of Wagner's reagent. Appearance of brown flocculent and precipitation reveals the presence of alkaloids.

Test for detection of tannins

1 ml of the extract was taken in a test tube, and then 1 ml of 0.1% ferric chloride containing 0.1 N HCl was added. Appearance of blue-black coloration indicates the presence of tannins.

Test for phenols

Few drops of ferric chloride were added to 1 ml of extract in a test tube. Development of dark green indicates the presence of phenols.

Test for flavonoids

To 1 ml of extract, 1 ml of dilute ammonia solution was added followed by the addition of concentrated H₂SO₄ dropwise. A yellow coloration observed indicates the presence of flavonoids.

Test for carbohydrates

Two test tubes were taken, one containing 1 ml of the extract to be tested and second tube containing 1 ml of glucose was used as a control. 1 ml of Fehling's Reagent was added to both the samples. Appearance of green, yellow, or red in plant extract reveals the presence of reducing sugars.

Test for glycosides (Keller-Kiliani test)

About 1 ml of extract was treated with 1 ml of glacial acetic acid containing one drop of ferric chloride solution. This was underlaid with 1 ml of concentrated H₂ SO₄. A brown ring at the interface indicates the presence of glycosides. Test for sterols About 2 ml of acetic anhydride was added to 1 ml crude extract of plant sample with 2 ml H₂SO₄. The color change from violet to blue or green indicates the presence of sterols.

Test for sterols

About 2 ml of acetic anhydride was added to 1 ml crude extract of plant sample with 2 ml H₂SO₄. The color change from violet to blue or green indicates the presence of sterols.

Table 1: Preliminary identification of phytochemical constituents from *Emblica officinalis* extract.

Phytochemicals	Observation
Alkaloids	-
Tannins	+
Proteins	-
Saponins	+
Quinones	-
Coumarins	-
Flavonoids	-
Phenols	+
Carbohydrates	+
Glycosides	+
Sterols	-

+: Present, -: Absent,

Worm collection

Indian adult earth worms (*Pheretima posthuma*) collected from moist soil and washed with normal saline to remove all matter. Earthworms of 3-5cm in length and 0.1-0.2cm width were used for the experimental protocol.

Standard drug

Albendazole 20 mg/ml was used as reference standard.

Anthelmintic assay

The earthworm divided into five groups, each group consisting six earthworms. The earthworms were first treated with in Normal Saline, than treated with albendazole (20mg/ml), ethanol and aqueous extract (100,150 mg/ml) of *Emblica officinalis* leaves. Observations are made for the time taken to paralysis and death of individual worms. Time for paralysis was noted when no movement could be observed except when the worms were shaken vigorously. Time for death of worms were recorded after ascertaining that worms neither moved when shaken vigorously nor when sprinkle the warm water (50^{0c}) followed by fading away of their body colors. [12].

Table 2: Anthelmintic activity of *Emblica officinalis* leaves extract.

Sr. No.	Groups	Treatment	Concentration	Time Taken For Paralysis (min)	Time Taken For Death (min)
1.	Control	Vehicle	-	-	-
		Normal saline solution	-	-	-
2.	Standard	Albendazole	20 mg/ml	19.76±0.47	24.11±0.26
3.		Ethanol	100 mg/ml	67.25±0.23	72.22±0.36
		Extract	10mg/ml	53.00±0.51	60.55±0.16
		Aqueous	100 mg/ml	61.18±0.41	66.31±0.22
	Test	Extract	150 mg/ml	47.13±0.70	52.36±0.41

DISCUSSION

This study revealed that leaves of *Emblica officinalis* have anthelmintic effect. Phytochemical analysis of the crude extract revealed the presence of tannins, phenolic compounds and flavonoids along with other chemical constituents contained within them. Tannins have been reported to produce anthelmintic activities. Aqueous extract shown better results compared to alcoholic extract of leaves of *Emblica officinalis*. Further pharmacological and biochemical investigation will clearly elucidate the mechanism of action and will be helpful in projecting this plant leaves as a therapeutic target in helminthes research. Further research work has to be carried out to isolate bioactive molecules responsible for their activity and to investigate and screen the compounds to evaluate other biological activities.

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